

Corrosion inhibition of mild steel by some pyrazole derivatives in aqueous HCl solutions

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The inhibitive properties of pyrazole derivatives (1-9) for corrosion of mild steel in 0.5 M HCl solution have been evaluated. For some derivatives the efficiency value is 97%. Langmuir absorption isotherm and Hammett substitution constants for these derivatives are in agreement with the galvanostatic measurements. Greater inhibition has been obtained with electron-withdrawing substituents than with electron-donating ones.

The inhibiting action exercised by organic compounds on the dissolution of metallic species is normally related to interactions by adsorption between the inhibitors and the metal surface. This process is considered as interface inhibition, according to Fischer's classification. Interface inhibition may hinder one or more of the partial reactions involved in the corrosion process. Thus many authors have postulated that the adsorption of the inhibitor results in an increase of the overpotential of the proton discharge process, or an increase in the ohmic resistance as a result of formation of an inhibitor film at the metal-electrolyte interface¹.

The present work proffers a better definition of the system through an analysis of the correlation between molecular structure and inhibitor characteristics. The possibility of correlating structural characteristics with the inhibitor properties of organic substances is justified by the fact that metal-inhibitor interactions are based on chemisorption. However, it is possible to assume a bond of the Lewis acid-base type, with the inhibitor as an electron donor and the metal as an electron acceptor². The electron density on the organic function group (atom), which can be defined as the reaction center for the establishment of the adsorption bond, is obviously important.

Organic compounds containing lone pairs and/or multiple bonds usually are effective inhibitors¹⁻³. Thus organic inhibitors are compounds with at least one polar function, having atoms of N,S,O and in some cases Se and P. In such case the adsorption bond strength is determined by the electron density of the atom acting as the reaction center and by the polarizability of the function group (atom). The effectiveness of the functional atoms with respect to the adsorption process, when the stabilities of the compounds are equal, follows the sequence^{4,6}: Se > S > N > O.

The idea of electron density acquires particular impor-

tance in aromatic, aliphatic amines and heterocyclic inhibitors, whose structures may be affected by the introduction of substituents in different positions of the ring. Hackeman developed a theory of adsorption based on numerous measurements carried out in the presence of secondary aliphatic amines and cyclic imines as inhibitors in acid medium^{2,4}. He concluded that the greater the percentage of η -orbitals of the free electrons on the N atom, the more effective the inhibition action is. However, Riggs and Every⁷, on the basis of their study of the inhibiting action of amines and thiols and some of their derivatives, obtained results inconsistent with the electron density theory assumption.

In the present work, the inhibition efficiency of some pyrazole derivatives (1-5) on the acid dissolution of mild steel was evaluated using the galvanostatic cathodic polarization technique.

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|--------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| 1 X = H, Y = H | 6 X = CH ₃ , Y = CN |
| 2 X = H, Y = Br | 7 X = CH ₃ -O-, Y = H |
| 3 X = H, Y = CN | 8 X = CH ₃ -O-, Y = Br |
| 4 X = CH ₃ , Y = H | 9 X = CH ₃ -O-, Y = CN |
| 5 X = CH ₃ , Y = Br | |

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 presents the galvanostatic cathodic polarization curves of mild steel electrode immersed in 0.5 M HCl solution containing different concentrations of compound 1. Similar polarization curves were obtained for the other eight compounds (not shown). As mentioned above, values of I_{corr} were obtained from the polarization curves by extrapolat-

Fig. 1. Galvanostatic cathodic polarization curves of mild steel in 0.5 M HCl containing different concentrations of compound 1 (PP) : (■) 0.00, (Δ) 5×10^{-6} , (○) 1×10^{-4} , (□) 1×10^{-5} and (●) 1×10^{-2} M.

ing the cathodic Tafel slopes to the respective corrosion potential (E_{corr}). The results are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Galvanostatic cathodic polarization data of mild steel in 0.5 M HCl solutions containing pyrazole derivatives as inhibitors

Compd. no.	Inhibitor concn. M	E_{corr} mV _{SCE}	i_{corr} A cm ⁻²	Surface coverage Q	PI %
1	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-519	1.3×10^{-4}	0.23	23
	10^{-5}	-506	1.2×10^{-4}	0.29	29.41
	10^{-4}	-469	8.0×10^{-5}	0.53	52.94
	10^{-3}	-440	2.1×10^{-5}	0.88	87.65
	10^{-2}	-405	1.5×10^{-5}	0.91	91
2	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-517	8.8×10^{-5}	0.48	48
	10^{-5}	-464	6.2×10^{-5}	0.64	63.53
	10^{-4}	-446	3.5×10^{-5}	0.74	74.41
	10^{-3}	-429	1.5×10^{-5}	0.91	91.18
	10^{-2}	-398	1.0×10^{-5}	0.94	94
3	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-530	2.0×10^{-4}	-0.2	60
	10^{-5}	-520	1.9×10^{-4}	-0.15	73.05
	10^{-4}	-500	1.7×10^{-4}	0	83.052
	10^{-3}	-472	1.5×10^{-4}	0.14	95.029
	10^{-2}	-461	1.0×10^{-4}	0.4	97
4	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-504	6.8×10^{-5}	0.6	52
	10^{-5}	-486	4.5×10^{-5}	0.74	64.07
	10^{-4}	-451	2.8×10^{-5}	0.84	81.017
	10^{-3}	-417	8.0×10^{-6}	0.95	92.35
	10^{-2}	-383	5.0×10^{-6}	0.97	95
5	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-507	8.2×10^{-5}	0.52	32.05
	10^{-5}	-490	6.0×10^{-5}	0.65	41.17
	10^{-4}	-451	3.2×10^{-5}	0.61	64.7
	10^{-3}	-421	1.3×10^{-5}	0.92	82.35
	10^{-2}	-390	8.5×10^{-6}	0.95	86

Table-1 (contd.)

6	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-510	1.2×10^{-4}	0.33	72
	10^{-5}	-495	1.0×10^{-4}	0.41	84
	10^{-4}	-461	6.0×10^{-5}	0.65	90
	10^{-3}	-426	3.0×10^{-5}	0.82	96.47
	10^{-2}	-395	2.4×10^{-5}	0.86	98
7	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-500	8.8×10^{-5}	0.72	64
	10^{-5}	-481	6.2×10^{-5}	0.84	81
	10^{-4}	-446	3.5×10^{-5}	0.9	88.23
	10^{-3}	-411	1.5×10^{-6}	0.97	92.35
	10^{-2}	-375	1.0×10^{-6}	0.98	97.87
8	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-505	6.0×10^{-5}	0.64	64
	10^{-5}	-490	3.2×10^{-5}	0.81	81
	10^{-4}	-452	2.0×10^{-5}	0.88	88.23
	10^{-3}	-417	1.3×10^{-5}	0.92	92.35
	10^{-2}	-385	3.6×10^{-6}	0.98	97.87
9	0	-527	1.7×10^{-4}	0	0
	5×10^{-6}	-505	6.8×10^{-5}	0.6	60
	10^{-5}	-490	3.6×10^{-5}	0.79	79
	10^{-4}	-452	2.6×10^{-5}	0.85	85
	10^{-3}	-417	1.6×10^{-5}	0.91	90.7
	10^{-2}	-385	1.1×10^{-5}	0.93	93.21

The compounds used were classified by two methods according to the nature of the substituents X and Y. The first method include those which have the same X but different Y and classified in three groups according to X : the first group is 1,2,3, the second group is 4,5,6 and the third group is 7,8,9. The second method contain those which have the same Y but different X and also classified in three groups according to Y : compounds 1,4,7 as first group, 2,5,8 as second group, and 3,6,9 as third group.

Fig. 2 reveals that percentage inhibition of compounds

Fig. 2. Plots of PI vs concentration of inhibitors for the dissolution of mild steel in 0.5 M HCl solution : (●) 4, (□) 5 and (○) 6.

4,5,6 increases with increasing additive concentration until reaching a limiting value. This value indicates the complete formation of a monolayer of the additive on the active sites. Those classified by the first method are : first group : 1 > 2 > 3; second group : 4 > 5 > 6, and third group : 7 > 8 > 9; while those by the second method are : first group : 1 < 4 < 7, second group : 2 < 5 < 8, and third group : 3 < 6 < 9.

The conclusion that optimum inhibition was obtained after formation of a monolayer on the metal surface was substantiated by plotting Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. A direct relation between the metal surface and the inhibitor molecules was proposed. The classical relation correlating the concentration of the adsorbates and of the adsorption is given by⁸

$$\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = ACe^{-Q/RT} \quad (1)$$

$$\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = \log A + \log C - \frac{Q}{2.303RT} \quad (2)$$

where *C* is the inhibitor concentration (*M*), θ the degree of inhibition, which is directly proportional to the fractional surface area covered with the inhibitor molecules. The values of surface coverage (θ) are calculated using eqn. (6). The log-log plots of the concentration vs $\theta/(1-\theta)$ for the various compounds are illustrated in Fig. 3. The straight lines indicate that the adsorption process occurred according to Langmuir's adsorption isotherms. This result supports the conclusion that maximum inhibition corresponds to the formation of a monolayer of the additive on the active sites of the metal surface.

It was clear from Table 1 that the corrosion rate decreases with the increase of inhibitor concentration. Also, E_{corr} shifted to a more positive direction, and I_{corr} values decreased with increasing inhibitor concentrations. These data indicate these organic additions slowed the corrosion rate, increased the cathodic overvoltage, and behaved predominantly as anodic inhibitors. This behaviour indicated that the first adsorbed molecules of the inhibitor were attached to the most active sites, usually considered to be the corners or edges of incomplete layers of atoms on the metal surface. This would have interfered with the anodic reaction by hindering the escape of Fe^{2+} ions from the metal surface into the solution, and the attack on the metal then would have proceeded at a reduced rate from less active anodic sites. With increasing concentration, more molecules would have been adsorbed due to Van der Waals forces between the inhibitor molecules. The increasing close-packed film thus built up would have inhibited the anodic reaction further by steric hindrance to the escape of Fe^{2+} . At this stage, there

was an inhibition of the cathodic reaction, probably as a result of steric hindrance of the combination of the adsorbed hydrogen atoms to form molecules. A similar mechanism was suggested by Arab and Noor⁹.

Fig. 3 and Table 1 show substitution of hydrogen in the *para*-position of a phenyl ring in the pyrazole derivatives by a methyl or methoxy group increases PI of the given compound. At the same concentration, PI of the methoxy-substituted compounds is higher than that of the methyl-substituted ones. On the other hand, the substitution of hydrogen by a bromo or cyano group in the 4-position in the pyrazole ring decreases PI of the pyrazole compounds. At the same concentration, the cyano-substituted compounds lowers PI more than bromo-substituted ones.

Fig. 3. Langmuir adsorption isotherms for the inhibitors (●) 4, (□) 5 and (○) 6

These results are explained on the basis of the change of electron density of the atoms acting as the reaction center by the substituents present in the phenyl rings or in the pyrazole ring.

Donahue and Nobe¹⁰ examined the mechanism of the action of organic corrosion inhibitors and showed that the protective properties of organic compounds in the case of the corrosion of Fe in sulfuric acid are a function of the Hammett and Taft constants. Comprehensive studies in this direction also were carried out by Grigor'ev *et al.*¹¹, who likewise related the inhibiting effect of organic compounds

to the nature of the substituent. According to Hammett, the ratio of the reaction rate constant for an organic compound with a substituent R (k_R) to the reaction rate constant of an organic compound of the same series without a substituent (k_0) is given by the equation¹²,

$$\log(k_R/k_0) = \rho\sigma \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the proportionality constant which depends on the nature of both the electrode and electrolyte solution, respectively; it is a measure of the sensitivity of a given series of compounds to impart inhibition action, and where constant σ (Hammett's constant) reflects the influence of substituent R on the electron density of the center of the molecule. It is negative in the case of an electron-donating substituent and positive when the substituent is electron-withdrawing; constant σ is constant for a given reaction series with a certain active center.

For Fe or Ni, Grigor'ev *et al.*¹¹ found that an increase in the electron-donor properties of the substituent (increase in the negative value of σ) in the benzaldehyde molecule tends to increase the inhibiting effect. They attributed this relationship to the difference between the effects of substituents shifting the electron density at an adsorption center on the physical and specific adsorption.

The aforementioned assumptions and explanation were substantiated by the results illustrated in Fig. 3. In a similar manner to the Hammett equation¹³, plotting of PI vs the substituent constant σ (for the unsubstituted pyrazole derivative [$\sigma = 0$], methylsubstituted derivative [$\sigma = -0.17$] and methoxy-substituted derivative [$\sigma = -0.27$]) at a given concentration, gave a straight-line (Fig. 4). The empirical equation obeyed for such variation is

$$PI = \rho\sigma \quad (4)$$

Results shown in Fig. 4 are in good agreement with the previously deduced conclusions.

Fig. 4. Variation of percentage inhibitors (PI%) with the substituent constant σ .

As mentioned above, the methoxy-substituted derivatives are more efficient than the methyl-substituted ones. This could also be discussed from the structural point of view; both methyl and methoxy groups have a positive substituent (+ R) effect but the inductive effects were positive (+ I) and negative (- I), respectively. Although the methyl group had + R , its effect is very small as a result of hyperconjugation, thus

In the case of the methoxy group, + R is large, as is - I , thus

The decrease in PI in the case of bromo and cyano substituents in the 4-position of a pyrazole ring may be discussed using the following assumptions. These groups (Br and CN) are electron-withdrawing and have negative inductive effect (- I). Their presence in an inhibitor molecule reduces the electron density at inhibitor adsorption centers, which in turn should reduce the specific adsorption on the metal surface. This state should reduce the efficiency of these derivatives, which is in good agreement with the obtained results.

Conclusions: The inhibition efficiency of some pyrazole derivatives on the acid dissolution of mild steel was evaluated using a galvanostatic cathodic polarization technique. PI increases with increasing additive concentration until reaching a limiting value. Optimum inhibition is obtained after formation of a monolayer on the metal surface. Thus, a direct relation between the metal surface and the inhibitor molecules is proposed. E_{corr} shifts to a more positive direction, and I_{corr} decreases with increasing inhibitor concentrations. These data indicate that organic addition slows the corrosion rate, increases the cathodic overvoltage, and behaves predominantly as anodic inhibitors. At the same concentration, PI of the methoxy-substituted compounds is higher than that of the methyl-substituted ones. On the other hand, the substitution of hydrogen by a bromo or cyano group in the 4-position in the pyrazole ring decreases PI of the

pyrazole compounds. At the same concentration, the cyano-substituted compounds lower PI more than bromo-substituted ones.

Experimental

These pyrazoles (1-9) were prepared purified, and identified according to the recommended methods¹⁴.

The percentage inhibition (PI) was calculated by

$$PI = \frac{(i_{\text{corr}})_{\text{uninhibited}} - (i_{\text{corr}})_{\text{inhibited}}}{(i_{\text{corr}})_{\text{uninhibited}}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where $(I_{\text{corr}})_{\text{uninhibited}}$ and $(I_{\text{corr}})_{\text{inhibited}}$ are the corrosion current densities in the absence and presence of inhibitor, respectively. The I_{corr} values were calculated by the Tafel extrapolation method. The degree of coverage (θ) was determined using the expression¹⁵,

$$\theta = 1 - \frac{(i_{\text{corr}})_{\text{inhibited}}}{(i_{\text{corr}})_{\text{uninhibited}}} \quad (6)$$

From the I_{corr} values (corrosion rates) of different inhibitor concentration, the respective isotherm values were obtained¹⁶.

Procedure : Specimens (1 cm × 2 cm) were prepared from mild steel sheet (0.1 cm in thickness) having the composition (wt%) : C, 0.20; Si, 0.15; Mn, 0.40; P, 0.017; S, 0.0189. These electrodes were fixed to pyrex glass tubing with Araldite. The electrical contact was achieved through thick copper wires soldered to the electrodes. The electrode was polished using emery papers, degreased with acetone and washed with double-distilled water. A platinum sheet (1 cm × 2 cm) was used as an auxiliary electrode. The electrolyte was 0.5 M HCl. Each experiment was repeated three times to ensure reproducibility.

Galvanostatic polarization measurement was carried out using a constant current unit (2 μ A – 1000 mA). The potential of the electrode was measured relative to saturated calomel electrode (SCE) using a Valve voltmeter (Heathkit, VVM, England).

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